

ISic1046

I.Sicily inscription 1046

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

relief

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Quarry ('Santicelli'), near Palazzolo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2273

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140525

1. Ἴσ[. . . . Φ]ύσκων [ος]
2. ἦ[ρως] ἀγαθός.
- 3.

Edition: PHI175457

1. Ἴσ [. Φ] ύσκων
2. ἦ[ρωες] ἀγαθοί.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492674

EDCS 39102200

PHI 140525

PHI 175457

Bibliography

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Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5462

Bernabò Brea, L. 1956. Akrai. Catania. At 147 no.12 fig.31.1

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabò Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.24

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